

Social Media Addiction Effects on Well-Being among Tertiary School Graders an Empirical Study in Viaskhapatnam

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ABSTRACT: Psychological well-being has become one of the crucial aspects of modern psychology. It has attracted not only psychologists but also medical practitioners in compliance with the mental health, emotions, depression, stress, etc. of the individual's academic and social life. Right from the existence of behavioral sciences, efforts have been made by researchers of different disciplines to get a deep understanding of the various and different dimensions and correlates of psychological well-being. Social media platforms are an online association site where individuals cooperate to construct, offer and change their thought and remarks concerning any data. Over the past decade, online long distance social networking communication has brought significant changes in the way people communicate and collaborate.

The study aimed to determine the impact of social media's early health issues such as student depression and anxiety.

A descriptive study was conducted among Tertiary level educated students in Visakhapatnam with a sample of 130 respondents. It included questions on demographical information, the pattern of social networking usage, social relationship, and health effects.

Results: Present study results found that there is a significant association between time spent on social media and the number of social networking apps. There is a positive correlation between Depression feelings with serious active on social networking apps than in real life.

Conclusion: This study concludes that more usage of social networking sites is affecting the Tertiary school student's well-being such as depression and anxiety.

KEYWORDS: Anxiety, Social media addiction, Social networking sites, Well-being depression

BACKGROUND

In today's era, social media has fallen into the trap of addiction, which is having a far-reaching impact. The current study examines social media addiction among 130 tertiary school students aged 13–19 years. Previous studies have highlighted that psychological symptoms such as anxiety, depression, shame, loneliness and boredom are strongly associated with people who use social media extensively.

Depression, anxiety, positive thinking and high energy well-being factors are common and are often not diagnosed in college students. Social networking sites have become popular among Tertiary graders and may even exhibit frustration and anxiety.

The aim of this study was to determine the impact of social media on wellness issues such as depression and anxiety in students. Social media engages in a variety of online networking; it's a simple movement that takes care of children and adolescents by improving communication.

Social networking sites offer different openings per day to interact with peers, school students, and people with common interests. (Ted Eaton 2010). Over the past 5 years, the size of teens and young adults using social networking sites has expanded significantly. According to a recent survey, 22% of teenagers sign up for their top choice social networking sites 10 times a day and most young people sign in to social media apps more than once a day. Seventy-five percent of young people currently use phones, 25% use social media, 54% use them for messaging and 24% use instant messaging. Thus, the social and living progress of this current era is taking place on the internet and cell telephones.

(Hinduja S, Pachin J, 2010). Recently, some experts have linked social networking sites with some mental disorders, including depression and anxiety. Since social networking sites are a new surprise, many inquiries about the potential impact on mental health have not been answered. (Igor Pontic, 2014).

INTRODUCTION

Social media engages in a variety of online networking; it is a general movement that asks about children and adolescents through communication, social association, and the development of specialized skills (Horst H, 2010). Social networking sites provide daily interactions with peers, schoolmates and people with common interests.

(Ted Eaton 2010). In the last 5 years, the number of students and pupils using social networking sites has expanded significantly. According to a recent survey, 22% of teens sign up for their top choice on social networking sites 10 times every day, and most young people sign up for social media apps more than once a day. Seventy-five percent of young people currently use phones, and 25% use them for social media, 54% use them for messaging and 24% use them for instant messaging. Thus, much of the social and vibrant progress of this age is taking place on the Internet and cell telephones.

(Hinduja S, Pachin J, 2010). Recently, some experts have included social networking sites related to certain mental disorders, including depression and anxiety. Since social networking sites are a new surprise, many inquiries about the potential impact on mental health have not been answered. (Igor Pentic, 2014). This research therefore minimizes the impact of social media on students' mental health issues.

Review of literature

Borens-Diaz, et al. (2019) shared that social media is the most dangerous phase for youth, where the use of youth for cyber bullying and trolling is dangerous for the mental health of the youth. A study by Williams and Tessedale (2018) found that people who use social media extensively are more likely to have mental health problems.

Oberst, et al. (2017) classifies the effects of online networking, which specifically affects the mental well-being of young people, overuse of Internet-based life leads to problems of emotional well-being. Another predator is bile; In contrast, various researchers have reported the pessimistic effects of online life such as the World Health Organization (2017) that people who have been using Internet-based life for some time are refreshed by the dangers they see besides Are on the future problems of a country.

Peter and Minot (2017) describe how social media can lead to hostile and insecure behavior in a way that is harmful to an individual's mental well-being, especially young people. The impact of internet based life depends on its usage if a person has more social media and anything that can harm him.

Parmar (2017) expressed that in the 21st century, youth are investing their energy in various social conflicts. Excitement media, including televisions, like telephones, PCs, workstations, and some other devices, are common 12–15 hours a day. With the help of these gadgets they are using WhatsApp, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and many more. According to 2019 data (Felix Richter, 2019), 2.7 billion people use Facebook, Instagram or Messenger every month and more than 2.1 billion people use at least one every day.

Over 1 billion of them are Facebook's dynamic customers, the use of this application is not very high among peers of all young people, customer bio information is available there and obscure friends can hack their information? There are only 1 billion YouTube dynamic subscribers, more than 4 million WhatsApp dynamic subscribers, plus 4 million Instagram permanent subscribers and over 3 million Twitter dynamic subscribers. Similarly, the size of the online life subscriber is expanding the real risk step for mental wellbeing of young people.

Hazardous online life consumption is strongly and independently associated with the effects of extended recession (Shenja et al. 2017). Thornacroft, et al. (2016) stated that online networking is important for the lives of young people because it has an unreliable connection to the emotional wellbeing of groups of people, but again some Ula Hanjit portrayal, the use of social networking sites for digital harassment for human mental well-being. It is exceptionally dangerous and dangerous for even young people to do so, imitate and will lose their confidence and self-confidence to others. This has led to some small positive effects of online networking among the younger generation.

Miller et al. (2016) illustrated that Internet-based life changes the approach to correspondence, which ties in addition to socialization. Despite its benefits of becoming a development group, investing its energy in a community involves some risks that are dangerous to their emotional health. Lane-Rios, et al. (2016) that social media is often used for long-distance interpersonal communication bookkeeping, which is not an awkward risk for adolescents, as regular use of person-to-person communication bookkeeping affects mental health during adolescence.

Patel, et al. (2016.) suggested that online networking is causing problems such as discomfort, drowsiness, and food problems. Furthermore, the use of social media is gradually becoming a problematic issue for young people, but they invest more of their

energy for social media applications and as a result they get nothing because it is the mental there is a great risk to health. Unnecessary use of SNS has been found to induce high levels of grief, discomfort, pain, depression, and depression over life, with this method abandoning mental well-being (Woods & Scott, 2016), while SM's Use has been fully extended.

Depression (Lin et al., 2016). The final detail was Townsend, and as expected by others. (2014) Thinking about how social media becomes a hindrance to people are usually alone when interacting with others, with the result that it is their instinct, tension, sadness and becomes a sign of self-depletion.

Jarman Molz and Paris, (2015) report that adolescents test life online in light as cutting-edge innovation engages them, as well as contributing to their aptitude for their peers, in addition to communicating with family, Which further increases their mental health. Gibson, et al. Zhang, et al. (2015) Correspondence and social association can promote social media life. Creeks (2015) showed that youth who increasingly use social media are usually in trouble and are regularly embarrassed and tired.

Amedi (2015) expressed that social media causes anxiety and depression in young people who suffer when clients treat others with hilarious and excessive office as they have become a psychological problem for young people. Like the clever Clark, Kuosmanen, and Barry (2015), social media enhances the experience of young people.

Gelenchik et al (2013) stated that there is no confirmation of correlation between SNS and clinical depression. Gelenchik researched the relationship between social networking use and depression in young people. According to their findings, there should be no doubt about the individual's relation to the use of social networking media in American adolescents. Mustafa Kok (2013) argues that extravagant coercion and discomfort certainly predispose to Facebook habit.

According to Gabre and Kumar (2012), Facebook increases feelings of anxiety and loses control among undergarments. Depression is an important risk factor for uncommon common heart problems and can significantly affect suicide. Similarly, this problem is a major reason for reckless work and thus it affects the financial condition of the individual, his family, as well as the general public (Lepine et al. 2011). Computer use and television viewing have been associated with anxiety and / or depressive symptoms (de Wit et al. 2011). Can cause feelings of depression and loneliness in Facebook understudies (Odell 2011). O'Keeffe, Clarke-Pearson, and the Council on Communications and Media (2011) recently classified the expression "Facebook Depression" as a long-term youth experience and unfortunate side effects through web-based networking media destinations is. As Moreno et al (2011a) suggests, Facebook utterances link the presence of side effects of depression to the client's basic types of depression.

Experimentation is one of the most frequent psychological problems in manufactured and low-wage countries. In an all-inclusive society, 16% of people experience significant depression at least several times in their lifetime (Lee et al. 2010). Depression is a disorder that is affecting more and more people (Burnsd, 2010). Depression is a disorder that is affecting more and more people, and can lead to suicide if left untreated (Mackall, 2007). In the first place, the evidence and isolation of the pessimistic consequences of the SNS habit are close to the well being of the household. To date, the pessimistic effect of SNS on home health, including mental health, has not been effectively investigated, as well as social and physical well-being (World Health Organization (WHO), 2006). There is an increased awareness of depression and sadness through repetition of comprehension treatments (Volcker, 2003). In addition to psychological behavioral patterns, innovation recommends applying customers' current offending insights.

Objectives of the present study

1. To investigate the social media addiction effects on Well-being dimensions among tertiary school students
Hypothesis
1. There will be an associated correlation with social media addiction and well-being among Tertiary educated students.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Descriptive research was considered for the present study. Tertiary educated student's data was collected for study purposes. Data was collected from the questionnaire method. The sample size collected was 130 tertiary educators. A simple random sampling method applied for the present study. A structured questionnaire was distributed to the participants. The first section included questions on demographic data and the second section included social media addiction questions which comprise various constructs like the pattern of social networking usage, time spent, everyday activity in social networking sites, engagement of social media apps, and second questionnaire well-being comprises various domains related questions such as depression and anxiety, energy and positive thinking

Methodology: For data collection, the tool used: The study used social media addiction to verify the purpose of statistical analysis. For detailed statistics, correlation, and more analysis, regression was performed considering social media addiction exists for another. Based variable.

Research design

Quantitative correlation studies using the survey method were used. A correlational study was used to determine whether there was a relationship between the two variables. It studies whether an increase or decrease in one variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in another variable. For further analysis, regression was performed to look at social media addiction as existed for other orienting variables.

Sample and Sample Design: Data were collected from a random sample of 130 Tertiary graders at various age groups of 16 to 22 years (M = 2.40, SD = 1.35) who responded to the survey generated using questionnaires. In this sample, 35.6% of the respondents were male and 64.4% were female (male = 78, female = 68).

Table-1 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.902	.903	25

The Social Media Addiction Scale was found to be a 5-point Likert type scale (Cronbeck's alpha coefficient) consisting of 25 items with an internal consistency coefficient. 902

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics for sample

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age	17 years	39	17.8	30.0	30.0
	18 years	47	21.5	36.2	66.2
	20 years	13	5.9	10.0	76.2
	21 years	16	7.3	12.3	88.5
	22 years	15	6.9	11.6	100.0
Gender	Male	78	35.6	60.0	60.0
	Female	52	23.7	40.0	100.0
No. of Social media apps Used	One app usage	7	3.2	5.4	5.4
	one and two apps usage	77	35.2	59.2	64.6
	more than two apps usage	46	21.0	35.4	100.0

The study was analyzed with correlation present to look at the detailed statistics, for further analysis was applied regression of social media addiction in order to base on variables to validate the hypothesis of statistical data.

Table 2: Correlational analysis among the variables Social Media Addiction, Well-Being domains

	Well-being depression	Well- being anxiety	Well-being positive thinking	Well-being energy
Social media addiction Pearson Correlation	-.210*	.032	-.049	-.030
Social media addiction Sig. (2-tailed)	.017	.719	.579	.733
Social media addiction N	130	130	130	130

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

RESULTS

Initially, a Correlation Analysis was conducted to find the relationship shared by Social Media Addiction, Well-being depression, Well-being anxiety, Well-being positive thinking, Well-being energy

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	92.971	12.252		7.588	.000
Wellbeing depression	-1.899	.815	-.218	-2.330	.021
Wellbeing anxiety	.115	.531	.019	.218	.828
Wellbeing positive thinking	.248	.737	.032	.336	.737
Wellbeing energy	-.090	.668	-.012	-.134	.893

a. Dependent Variable: Social media addiction
 obtained Results showed that there was a significant negative association with Social Media Addiction and Depression ($r = -.210^*$; $p < 0.01$) and non-significant association with Well-being anxiety, Well-being positive thinking, Well-being energy

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.205 ^a	.042	.011	16.53358

The results show that Social Media Addiction could predict depression with significant accuracy ($R = 0.205$, $R^2 = 0.04$, Adjusted $r^2 = 0.011$, $F = 1.478$, $.213NS$)

DISCUSSION

The first section of the questionnaire enquired for how much social media is used by each respondent on a daily basis. This was asked to get a quantitative measure of the social media access and to obtain amongst the study group. In the study population it was found that the average of social media usage ranged between 3 to 10 hours. The Results suggested a negative correlation between social media addiction and depression i.e. No significant correlation was found between social media and Well-being anxiety, positive thinking. This study supported by previous study findings of Moreno, M.A., Zelenchik (2011) suggest that people who receive online reinforcement from their friends may have the opportunity to publicly discuss their depressive symptoms on Facebook. Two hundred profiles were evaluated and the average age of 20-year profile owners was 43.5%. Overall, depressive symptoms were seen in 25% of the profiles and 2.5% met the criteria for MDE. Profile owners are more likely to indicate frustration if there is at least one online response from their friends to a status update that reveals depressive symptoms. Social networking sites are an innovative way to deal with stigma about mental networking conditions, or to identify depressed students, based on the frequency of displaying depression symptoms in a public profile.

CONCLUSION As per the obtained results of the Correlation Hypothesis Partially significant that there was a significant negative relationship between Social Media Addiction and depression. Present study concluded that there was no relationship between Social Media Addiction and anxiety and also positive thinking.

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